

PRISMA 2020 Checklist

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Location where item is reported
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a systematic review.	Title
ABSTRACT			
Abstract	2	See the PRISMA 2020 for Abstracts checklist.	Supplementary File 2
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of existing knowledge.	Introduction
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of the objective(s) or question(s) the review addresses.	Introduction
METHODS			
Eligibility criteria	5	Specify the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the review and how studies were grouped for the syntheses.	Methods (study selection)
Information sources	6	Specify all databases, registers, websites, organisations, reference lists and other sources searched or consulted to identify studies. Specify the date when each source was last searched or consulted.	Methods (search strategy), Supplementary File 4
Search strategy	7	Present the full search strategies for all databases, registers and websites, including any filters and limits used.	Supplementary File 4
Selection process	8	Specify the methods used to decide whether a study met the inclusion criteria of the review, including how many reviewers screened each record and each report retrieved, whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	Methods (study selection)
Data collection process	9	Specify the methods used to collect data from reports, including how many reviewers collected data from each report, whether they worked independently, any processes for obtaining or confirming data from study investigators, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	Methods (data extraction)
Data items	10a	List and define all outcomes for which data were sought. Specify whether all results that were compatible with each outcome domain in each study were sought (e.g. for all measures, time points, analyses), and if not, the methods used to decide which results to collect.	Methods (data extraction)
	10b	List and define all other variables for which data were sought (e.g. participant and intervention characteristics, funding sources). Describe any assumptions made about any missing or unclear information.	Methods (data extraction)
Study risk of bias assessment	11	Specify the methods used to assess risk of bias in the included studies, including details of the tool(s) used, how many reviewers assessed each study and whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	Methods (quality assessment)
Effect measures	12	Specify for each outcome the effect measure(s) (e.g. risk ratio, mean difference) used in the synthesis or presentation of results.	Methods (statistical analysis)
Synthesis methods	13a	Describe the processes used to decide which studies were eligible for each synthesis (e.g. tabulating the study intervention characteristics and comparing against the planned groups for each synthesis (item #5)).	Methods (data extraction)
	13b	Describe any methods required to prepare the data for presentation or synthesis, such as handling of missing summary statistics, or data conversions.	Methods (data extraction and statistical analysis)
	13c	Describe any methods used to tabulate or visually display results of individual studies and syntheses.	Methods (statistical analysis)
	13d	Describe any methods used to synthesize results and provide a rationale for the choice(s). If meta-analysis was performed, describe the model(s), method(s) to identify the presence and extent of statistical heterogeneity, and software package(s) used.	Methods (statistical analysis)
	13e	Describe any methods used to explore possible causes of heterogeneity among study results (e.g. subgroup analysis, meta-regression).	Methods (statistical analysis)

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Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Location where item is reported
	13f	Describe any sensitivity analyses conducted to assess robustness of the synthesized results.	Methods (statistical analysis)
Reporting bias assessment	14	Describe any methods used to assess risk of bias due to missing results in a synthesis (arising from reporting biases).	not applicable
Certainty assessment	15	Describe any methods used to assess certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for an outcome.	Methods (statistical analysis)
RESULTS			
Study selection	16a	Describe the results of the search and selection process, from the number of records identified in the search to the number of studies included in the review, ideally using a flow diagram.	Supplementary File 5
	16b	Cite studies that might appear to meet the inclusion criteria, but which were excluded, and explain why they were excluded.	not applicable
Study characteristics	17	Cite each included study and present its characteristics.	Table 1
Risk of bias in studies	18	Present assessments of risk of bias for each included study.	Supplementary File 8
Results of individual studies	19	For all outcomes, present, for each study: (a) summary statistics for each group (where appropriate) and (b) an effect estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval), ideally using structured tables or plots.	Results
Results of syntheses	20a	For each synthesis, briefly summarise the characteristics and risk of bias among contributing studies.	Results (described separately for each outcome)
	20b	Present results of all statistical syntheses conducted. If meta-analysis was done, present for each the summary estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval) and measures of statistical heterogeneity. If comparing groups, describe the direction of the effect.	Results, Figure 1, Figure 2, Supplementary File 9, Supplementary File 10
	20c	Present results of all investigations of possible causes of heterogeneity among study results.	Results (described separately for each outcome)
	20d	Present results of all sensitivity analyses conducted to assess the robustness of the synthesized results.	Results (sensitivity analyses)
Reporting biases	21	Present assessments of risk of bias due to missing results (arising from reporting biases) for each synthesis assessed.	not applicable
Certainty of evidence	22	Present assessments of certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for each outcome assessed.	Results (described separately for each outcome)
DISCUSSION			
Discussion	23a	Provide a general interpretation of the results in the context of other evidence.	Discussion
	23b	Discuss any limitations of the evidence included in the review.	Discussion
	23c	Discuss any limitations of the review processes used.	Discussion
	23d	Discuss implications of the results for practice, policy, and future research.	Discussion
OTHER INFORMATION			
Registration and protocol	24a	Provide registration information for the review, including register name and registration number, or state that the review was not registered.	PROSPERO: CRD42023439666

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Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Location where item is reported
	24b	Indicate where the review protocol can be accessed, or state that a protocol was not prepared.	PROSPERO: CRD42023439666
	24c	Describe and explain any amendments to information provided at registration or in the protocol.	Methods; Results
Support	25	Describe sources of financial or non-financial support for the review, and the role of the funders or sponsors in the review.	Funding
Competing interests	26	Declare any competing interests of review authors.	Acknowledgements
Availability of data, code and other materials	27	Report which of the following are publicly available and where they can be found: template data collection forms; data extracted from included studies; data used for all analyses; analytic code; any other materials used in the review.	Data sharing statement

From: Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71
For more information, visit: <http://www.prisma-statement.org/>

PRISMA 2020 for Abstracts Checklist

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Reported (Yes/No)
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a systematic review.	Yes
BACKGROUND			
Objectives	2	Provide an explicit statement of the main objective(s) or question(s) the review addresses.	Yes
METHODS			
Eligibility criteria	3	Specify the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the review.	Yes
Information sources	4	Specify the information sources (e.g. databases, registers) used to identify studies and the date when each was last searched.	Yes
Risk of bias	5	Specify the methods used to assess risk of bias in the included studies.	Yes
Synthesis of results	6	Specify the methods used to present and synthesise results.	Yes
RESULTS			
Included studies	7	Give the total number of included studies and participants and summarise relevant characteristics of studies.	Yes
Synthesis of results	8	Present results for main outcomes, preferably indicating the number of included studies and participants for each. If meta-analysis was done, report the summary estimate and confidence/credible interval. If comparing groups, indicate the direction of the effect (i.e. which group is favoured).	Yes
DISCUSSION			
Limitations of evidence	9	Provide a brief summary of the limitations of the evidence included in the review (e.g. study risk of bias, inconsistency and imprecision).	Yes
Interpretation	10	Provide a general interpretation of the results and important implications.	Yes
OTHER			
Funding	11	Specify the primary source of funding for the review.	Yes
Registration	12	Provide the register name and registration number.	Yes

From: Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71

For more information, visit: <http://www.prisma-statement.org/>

Supplementary File 3. Research question

PICOS framework used in the process of formulating the research question:

The study will include patients with structural heart disease and therapy-refractory ventricular tachycardia (population) treated with stereotactic arrhythmia radioablation (STAR) (intervention), in single-arm trials or compared with any standard-of-care therapy (comparison). The main outcomes of interest are safety defined as the occurrence of likely, probably and definitely treatment-related grade 3 or higher adverse events, overall survival, and efficacy defined as VT burden reduction (50%, 75% and 95% thresholds) and time to VT recurrence (outcomes) reported in prospective trials, including final or interim reports (study type).

Supplementary File 4 - Search Strategy

Database(s): **Ovid MEDLINE(R) and Epub Ahead of Print, In-Process & Other Non-Indexed Citations and Ovid MEDLINE(R) Daily** 1946 to September 08, 2023 (limited to August 31, 2023). Search strategy executed on **2023-09-11**.

#	Searches	Results
1	arrhythmias, cardiac/ or atrial fibrillation/ or atrial flutter/ or exp cardiac complexes, premature/ or bundle-branch block/ or interatrial block/ or parasystole/ or wolff-parkinson-white syndrome/ or exp tachycardia/ or ventricular fibrillation/ or ventricular flutter/	205471
2	heart conduction system/ or atrioventricular node/ or sinoatrial node/ or accessory atrioventricular bundle/	42508
3	pulmonary veins/re, su	6526
4	(((cardiac or heart or atri* or auric* or AV or A-V or ventric* or supraventr* or LA or LV or external or events or ectopic or reciproc* or junctional or sinus) adj9 (fibrillat* or flutter* or ar?hythm* or tachycard* or tachyar?h* or tachy-ar?h* or preexcitat* or pre-excitat*)) or (torsade adj2 point*) or AIVR or ((idioventr* or idio-ventr*) adj3 rhythm*)).tw,kf.	210730
5	ar?hythmogen*.tw,kf.	13216
6	((VT or VTs) adj2 (scar* or VF or AF or exit site* or epicard* or cardiomyo* or isch?em* or episod* or sustain* or burden or ablat* or radioablat* or radiosurg* or radio-surg*)).tw,kf.	4588
7	(((prematur* or pre-matur* or ectopic* or echo) adj3 (beat* or heartbeat* or ((cardiac or atrial or ventric*) adj2 (complex* or contraction*)))) or PVC-burden or PVCs or extra-systol* or extrasystol* or late potentials or ventricular LP*).tw,kf.	16051
8	(parasystol* or para-systol* or (electric* adj2 storm*) or ((slow* or intermediat*) adj2 (pathway* or junction* or conduction*))).tw,kf.	8687
9	(((AV or A-V or atrioventr* or atrio-ventr* or sinoatrial or sino-atrial or interatrial or inter-atrial or (card* adj3 conduct*)) adj6 (node or nodes or nodal or junction* or pathway* or conduct* or interrupt* or block* or reentr* or re-entr* or antegrad* or reciproc* or orthodromic* or rhythm*)) or ((epicard* or endocard*) adj3 exit) or (nodal adj2 reentr*)).tw,kf.	38589
10	(((accessory or alternativ*) adj3 (AV or A-V or atrio-ventr* or atrioventr* or connection or conduct*)) or (accessory adj3 pathway*) or AP-ablat* or ((parahis* or atriohis*) adj2 (bypass* or tract*)) or (bundle adj2 Kent) or (mahaim adj2 fib*) or ((heart or card*) adj2 conduction*)).tw,kf.	11073
11	(Wolff-Parkinson-White or WPW or ((ventric* or cardiac or syndrom*) adj6 (preexcitat* or excitat*)) or (bundle adj2 block*)).tw,kf.	19075
12	(((pulm* adj2 (vein or venous)) or PV or PVI or RSPV) adj4 (isolat* or tissue* or junction* or antrum or ostia or ostium or tissue or amplitud* or ablat* or radioablat* or radiosurg* or radio-surg* or radiat*)) or PVAI* or CPVI*).tw,kf.	8267
13	or/1-12 [cardiac arrhythmias]	335355
14	exp heavy ion radiotherapy/ or radiosurgery/ or exp radiotherapy, high-energy/ or exp radiotherapy, conformal/	60176

15	heavy ions/ or ((exp radiotherapy/ or radiation dosage/ or rt.fs.) and photons/)	4979
16	(exp radiotherapy, computer-assisted/ or radiotherapy, image-guided/) and (ablation techniques/ or exp arrhythmias, cardiac/rt or exp heart conduction system/re or photons/ or stereotaxic techniques/)	2050
17	(radioablat* or radiosurg* or (radio adj (ablat* or surg*)) or (radiother* adj5 ablat*)).tw,kf.	18800
18	((non-invasiv* or noninvasiv* or ablat*) adj2 cardiac adj1 (radiat* or irradiat*)).tw,kf.	3
19	((catheter* adj1 free) not (stuck* adj6 catheter*)).tw,kf.	387
20	((stereotact* and (radiother* or irradiat* or radiat* or ablat*)) or SBRT or SABR).tw,kf.	20709
21	((multi-leaf or multileaf) adj2 collimator*) or MLC-track*).tw,kf.	2378
22	((heavy or carbon or C12 or C-12 or 12C or 12-C) adj3 ion*) or THIR).tw,kf. not ((heavy adj3 metal*) or carbon dioxid*).mp.	8844
23	((photon* or proton* or ion* or particle* or carbon* or C12 or C-12 or 12C or 12-C) adj2 (beam* or irradiat*)).tw,kf.	25349
24	((proton* adj3 (therap* or radiother* or ablat*)) not proton-pump*).tw,kf.	7413
25	(Cyberknife or Cyber-knife or Cyberheart or Cyber-heart).tw,kf.	1940
26	or/14-25 [radioablation]	102394
27	((cancer* or carcinom* or adenocarcinom* or tumo?r* or neoplas* or malignan* or sarcom* or leiomyosarcom* or adenom* or metasta* or neoadjuv* or neo-adjuv* or chemother* or cyostat* or checkpoint inhib* or prostat* or breast* or mastect* or postmastect* or thorax or thoracic or mediastin* or lobectom* or mesotheliom* or NSCLC* or cholangiocarcinom* or lymphom* or leuk?em* or AML or melanom* or schwannom* or NF2 or neurofibrom* or paragangliom* or gliom* or glioblastom*) not (fibrillat* or flutter or arrhythm* or tachycard* or cardiac or sinus or atrioventr* or atrium or ventricul*)).ti,ot. [cancer (therapy) in title]	3254688
28	26 not 27 [radioablation (not cancer therapy as main topic)]	58697
29	13 and 28 [I cardiac arrhythmias & radiotherapy]	334
30	(RRPVI* or RR-PVI*).tw,kf. [II robotic radiosurgical pulmonary vein isolation]	1
31	((stereotact* or STAR) adj3 ar?hythmi* adj2 (radioablat* or radioablat*)).tw,kf.	45
32	30 or 31 [II robotic radiosurgical pulmonary vein isolation / STAR]	46
33	29 or 32 [I II cardiac arrhythmias & radiotherapy]	334
34	remove duplicates from 33 [I II cardiac arrhythmias & radiotherapy -deduplicated]	334
35	limit 34 to dt=19460101-20230831 [January 1st, 1946 - August 31st, 2023]	332
36	limit 34 to rd=19460101-20230831 [January 1st, 1946 - August 31st, 2023]	331
37	35 or 36	332

Database(s): **Embase Classic+Embase** 1947 to September 08, 2023 (limited to August 31, 2023). Search strategy executed on: **2023-09-11**.

#	Searches	Results
1	(arrhythmogenesis/ or heart arrhythmia/ or atrioventricular junction arrhythmia/ or exp experimental arrhythmia/ or heart fibrillation/ or exp atrial fibrillation/ or exp heart ventricle fibrillation/ or *tachycardia/ or heart ventricle tachycardia/ or exp paroxysmal tachycardia/ or polymorphic ventricular tachycardia/ or monomorphic ventricular tachycardia/ or exp reentry tachycardia/ or sinus tachycardia/ or exp supraventricular tachycardia/ or heart atrium arrhythmia/ or heart atrium flutter/ or heart supraventricular arrhythmia/ or supraventricular premature beat/ or heart ventricle arrhythmia/ or heart ventricle extrasystole/ or heart ventricle flutter/ or parasystole/ or reentry arrhythmia/ or heart muscle conduction disturbance/ or heart accessory conduction pathway/ or exp heart bundle branch block/ or interatrial block/ or torsade des pointes/) not exp heart arrhythmia/si	430226
2	(exp heart muscle conduction system/ or exp heart conduction/) not exp heart arrhythmia/si	54792
3	pulmonary vein isolation/ or pulmonary veins/su	12862
4	((((cardiac or heart or atri* or auric* or AV or A-V or ventric* or supraventr* or LA or LV or external or events or ectopic or reciproc* or junctional or sinus) adj9 (fibrillat* or flutter* or ar?hythm* or tachycard* or tachyar?h* or tachy-ar?h* or preexcitat* or pre-excitat*)) or (torsade adj2 point*) or AIVR or ((idioventr* or idio-ventr*) adj3 rhythm*)).tw,kw.	343982
5	ar?hythmogen*.tw,kw.	20533
6	((VT or VTs) adj2 (scar* or VF or AF or exit site* or epicard* or cardiomyo* or isch?em* or episod* or sustain* or burden or ablat* or radioablat* or radiosurg* or radio-surg*)).tw,kw.	10913
7	((((prematur* or pre-matur* or ectopic* or echo) adj3 (beat* or heartbeat* or ((cardiac or atrial or ventric*) adj2 (complex* or contraction*)))) or PVC-burden or PVCs or extra-systol* or extrasystol* or late potentials or ventricular LP*).tw,kw.	25864
8	(parasystol* or para-systol* or (electric* adj2 storm*) or ((slow* or intermediat*) adj2 (pathway* or junction* or conduction*))).tw,kw.	12420
9	((((AV or A-V or atrioventr* or atrio-ventr* or sinoatrial or sino-atrial or interatrial or inter-atrial or (card* adj3 conduct*)) adj6 (node or nodes or nodal or junction* or pathway* or conduct* or interrupt* or block* or reentr* or re-entr* or antegrad* or reciproc* or orthodromic* or rhythm*)) or ((epicard* or endocard*) adj3 exit) or (nodal adj2 reentr*)).tw,kw.	59029
10	((((accessory or alternativ*) adj3 (AV or A-V or atrio-ventr* or atrioventr* or connection or conduct*)) or (accessory adj3 pathway*) or AP-ablat* or ((parahis* or atriohis*) adj2 (bypass* or tract*)) or (bundle adj2 Kent) or (mahaim adj2 fib*) or ((heart or card*) adj2 conduction*)).tw,kw.	14866
11	(Wolff-Parkinson-White or WPW or ((ventric* or cardiac or syndrom*) adj6 (preexcitat* or excitat*)) or (bundle adj2 block*)).tw,kw.	29899
12	(((((pulm* adj2 (vein or venous)) or PV or PVI or RSPV) adj4 (isolat* or tissue* or junction* or antrum or ostia or ostium or tissue or amplitud* or ablat* or radioablat* or radiosurg* or radio-surg* or radiat*)) or PVAI* or CPVI*).tw,kw.	16127
13	or/1-12 [cardiac arrhythmias]	592421

14	radiosurgery/ or gamma knife radiosurgery/ or stereotactic body radiation therapy/ or stereotactic radiosurgery/ or intensity modulated radiation therapy/ or ion therapy/ or photon therapy/ or proton therapy/	98504
15	radiosurgery equipment/ or gamma knife/ or cyberknife/ or multileaf collimator/	8832
16	megavoltage radiotherapy/ or heavy ions/	8039
17	ablation techniques/ and radiotherapy/	470
18	(radioablat* or radiosurg* or (radio adj (ablat* or surg*)) or (radiother* adj5 ablat*)).tw,ot,kw,dq.	29407
19	((non-invasiv* or noninvasiv* or ablat*) adj2 cardiac adj1 (radiat* or irradiat*)).tw,kw.	13
20	((catheter* adj1 free) not (stuck* adj6 catheter*)).tw,kw,dq.	766
21	((stereotact* and (radiother* or irradiat* or radiat* or ablat*)) or SBRT or SABR).tw,kw,dq.	39063
22	((multi-leaf or multileaf) adj2 collimator*) or MLC-track*).tw,kw.	3417
23	((heavy or carbon or C12 or C-12 or 12C or 12-C) adj3 ion*) or THIR).tw,kw. not ((heavy adj3 metal*) or carbon dioxid*).mp.	9137
24	((photon* or proton* or ion* or particle* or carbon* or C12 or C-12 or 12C or 12-C) adj2 (beam* or irradiat*)).tw,kw,dq.	31099
25	((proton* adj3 (therap* or radiother* or ablat*)) not proton-pump*).tw,kw.	12536
26	(Cyberknife or Cyber-knife or Cyberheart or Cyber-heart).tw,kw.	3739
27	or/14-26 [radioablation]	150501
28	((cancer* or carcinom* or adenocarcinom* or tumor* or neoplas* or malignan* or sarcom* or leiomyosarcom* or adenom* or metasta* or neoadjuv* or neo-adjuv* or chemother* or cytostat* or checkpoint inhib* or prostat* or breast* or mastect* or postmastect* or thorax or thoracic or mediastin* or lobectom* or mesotheliom* or NSCLC* or cholangiocarcinom* or lymphom* or leuk?em* or AML or melanom* or schwannom* or NF2 or neurofibrom* or paragangliom* or gliom* or glioblastom*) not (fibrillat* or flutter or arrhythm* or tachycard* or cardiac or sinus or atrioventr* or atrium or ventricul*)).ti,ot. [cancer (therapy) in title]	4471298
29	27 not 28 [radioablation (not cancer therapy as main topic)]	75867
30	13 and 29 [I cardiac arrhythmias & radiotherapy]	874
31	(RRPVI* or RR-PVI*).tw,kw. [II robotic radiosurgical pulmonary vein isolation]	0
32	((stereotact* or STAR) adj3 ar?hythmi* adj2 (radioablat* or radioablat*)).tw,kw.	98
33	31 or 32 [II robotic radiosurgical pulmonary vein isolation / STAR]	98
34	30 or 33 [I II cardiac arrhythmias & radiotherapy]	875
35	remove duplicates from 34 [I II cardiac arrhythmias & radiotherapy -deduplicated]	868
36	limit 35 to dd=19460101-20230831 [January 1st, 1946 - August 31st, 2023]	444

37	limit 35 to rd=19460101-20230831 [January 1st, 1946 - August 31st, 2023]	419
38	36 or 37	863

Database(s): **Web of Science (Core Collection)**. Search strategy executed on **2023-09-11**.

#5	441	#3 NOT #4 DOCTYPE=ALL DOCUMENT TYPES; LANGUAGE=ALL LANGUAGES;
#4	3,587,396	TI=((cancer* OR carcinom* OR adenocarcinom* OR tumor* OR tumour* OR neoplas* OR malignan* OR sarcom* OR leiomyosarcom* OR adenom* OR metasta* OR neoadjuv* OR (neo-adjuv*) OR chemother* OR cytostat* OR (checkpoint-inhib*) OR prostat* OR breast* OR mastect* OR postmastect* OR thorax OR thoracic OR mediastin* OR lobectom* OR mesotheliom* OR NSCLC* OR cholangiocarcinom* OR lymphom* OR leukem* OR leukaem* OR AML OR melanom* OR schwannom* OR NF2 OR neurofibrom* OR paragangliom* OR gliom* OR glioblastom*) NOT (fibrillat* OR flutter OR arrhythm* OR tachycard* OR cardiac OR sinus OR atrioventr* OR atrium OR ventricul*)) <i>DocType=All document types; Language=All languages;</i>
#3	468	#1 AND #2 <i>DocType=All document types; Language=All languages;</i>
#2	256,391	TS=(radioablat* OR radiosurg* OR radio-ablat* OR radio-surg* OR (radiother* NEAR/5 ablat*) OR ((non-invasiv* OR noninvasiv* OR ablat*) NEAR/2 cardiac NEAR/1 (radiat* OR irradiat*)) OR ((catheter* NEAR/1 free) NOT (stuck* NEAR/6 catheter*)) OR (stereotact* AND (radiother* OR irradiat* OR radiat* OR ablat*)) OR SBRT OR SABR OR ((multi-leaf OR multileaf) NEAR/2 collimator*) OR MLC-track* OR (((heavy OR carbon OR C12 OR C-12 OR 12C OR 12-C) NEAR/3 ion*) OR THIR) NOT ((heavy NEAR/3 metal*) OR carbon-dioxid*) OR ((photon* OR proton* OR ion* OR particle* OR carbon* OR C12 OR C-12 OR 12C OR 12-C) NEAR/2 (beam* OR irradiat*)) OR ((proton* NEAR/3 (therap* OR radiother* OR ablat*)) NOT proton-pump*) OR Cyberknife OR Cyber-knife OR Cyberheart OR Cyber-heart) <i>DocType=All document types; Language=All languages;</i>
#1	297,129	TS=(((cardiac OR heart OR atri* OR auric* OR AV OR A-V OR ventric* OR supraventr* OR LA OR LV OR external OR events OR ectopic OR reciproc* OR junctional OR sinus) NEAR/9 (fibrillat* OR flutter* OR arrhythm* OR tachycard* OR tachyarrh* OR tachy-arrh* OR preexcitat* OR pre-excitat*)) OR (torsade NEAR/2 point*) OR AIVR OR ((idioventr* OR idio-ventr*) NEAR/3 rhythm*) OR arrhythmogen* OR ((VT OR VTs) NEAR/2 (scar* OR VF OR AF OR exit-site* OR epicard* OR cardiomyo* OR isch*em* OR episod* OR sustain* OR burden OR ablat* OR radioablat* OR radiosurg* OR radio-surg*)) or ((prematu* or pre-matur* or ectopic* or echo) NEAR/3 (beat* or heartbeat*)) or ((cardiac or atrial or ventric*) NEAR/2 (complex* or contraction*)) or PVC-burden or PVCs or extra-systol* or extrasystol* or late-potentials or ventricular-LP* or parasystol* or para-systol* or (electric* NEAR/2 storm*) or ((slow* or intermediat*) NEAR/2 (pathway* or junction* or conduction*)) or ((AV or A-V or atrioventr* or atrio-ventr* or sinoatrial or sino-atrial or interatrial or inter-atrial or (card* NEAR/3 conduct*)) NEAR/6 (node or nodes or nodal or junction* or pathway* or conduct* or interrupt* or block* or reentr* or re-entr* or antegrad* or reciproc* or orthodromic* or rhythm*)) or ((epicard* or endocard*) NEAR/3 exit) or (nodal NEAR/2 reentr*) or ((accessory or alternativ*) NEAR/3 (AV or A-V or atrio-ventr* or atrioventr* or connection or conduct*)) or (accessory NEAR/3 pathway*) or AP-ablat* or ((parahis* or atriohis*) NEAR/2 (bypass* or tract*)) or

	(bundle NEAR/2 Kent) or (mahaim NEAR/2 fib*) or ((heart or card*) NEAR/2 conduction*) or Wolff-Parkinson-White or WPW or ((ventric* or cardiac or syndrom*) NEAR/6 (preexcitat* or excitat*)) or (bundle NEAR/2 block*) or (((pulm* NEAR/2 (vein or venous)) or PV or PVI or RSPV) NEAR/4 (isolat* or tissue* or junction* or antrum or ostia or ostium or tissue or amplitud* or ablat* or radioablat* or radiosurg* or radio-surg* or radiat*)) or PVAI* or CPVI*) <i>DocType=All document types; Language=All languages;</i>
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Database(s): **Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials**. Search strategy executed on: **2023-09-11**.

#	Searches	Results
1	(((cardiac or heart or atri* or auric* or AV or (A NEXT V) or ventric* or supraventr* or LA or LV or external or events or ectopic or reciproc* or junctional or sinus) near/9 (fibrillat* or flutter* or arrhythm* or tachycard* or tachyarrh* or (tachy NEXT arrh*) or preexcitat* or (pre NEXT excitat*))) or (torsade near/2 point*) or AIVR or ((idioventr* or (idio NEXT ventr*)) near/3 rhythm*)):ti,ab,kw	27838
2	arrhythmogen*:ti,ab,kw	456
3	((VT or VTs) near/2 (scar* or VF or AF or (exit NEAR site*) or epicard* or cardiomyo* or ischem* or ischaem* or episod* or sustain* or burden or ablat* or radioablat* or radiosurg* or (radio NEXT surg*)):ti,ab,kw	550
4	(((prematur* or (pre NEXT matur*) or ectopic* or echo) near/3 (beat* or heartbeat* or ((cardiac or atrial or ventric*) near/2 (complex* or contraction*)))) or (PVC NEXT burden) or PVCs or (extra NEXT systol*) or extrasystol* or (late NEXT potentials) or (ventricular NEXT LP*)):ti,ab,kw	1973
5	(parasystol* or (para NEXT systol*) or (electric* near/2 storm*) or ((slow* or intermediat*) near/2 (pathway* or junction* or conduction*)):ti,ab,kw	187
6	(((AV or (A NEXT V) or atrioventr* or (atrio NEXT ventr*) or sinoatrial or (sino NEXT atrial) or interatrial or (inter NEXT atrial) or (card* near/3 conduct*)) near/6 (node or nodes or nodal or junction* or pathway* or conduct* or interrupt* or block* or reentr* or (re NEXT entr*) or antegrad* or reciproc* or orthodromic* or rhythm*)) or ((epicard* or endocard*) near/3 exit) or (nodal near/2 reentr*)):ti,ab,kw	2925
7	(((accessory or alternativ*) near/3 (AV or (A NEXT V) or (atrio NEXT ventr*) or atrioventr* or connection or conduct*)) or (accessory near/3 pathway*) or (AP NEXT ablat*) or ((parahis* or atriohis*) near/2 (bypass* or tract*)) or (bundle near/2 Kent) or (mahaim near/2 fib*) or ((heart or card*) near/2 conduction*)):ti,ab,kw	1408
8	(Wolff NEXT Parkinson NEXT White or WPW or ((ventric* or cardiac or syndrom*) near/6 (preexcitat* or excitat*)) or (bundle near/2 block*)):ti,ab,kw	1053
9	(((pulm* near/2 (vein or venous)) or PV or PVI or RSPV) near/4 (isolat* or tissue* or junction* or antrum or ostia or ostium or tissue or amplitud* or ablat* or radioablat* or radiosurg* or (radio NEXT surg*) or radiat*)) or PVAI* or CPVI*):ti,ab,kw	1803
10	{or #1-#9} [cardiac arrhythmias]	31340

11	((radioablat* or radiosurg* or (radio NEXT (ablat* or surg*)) or (radiother* near/5 ablat*)):ti,ab,kw	1464
12	((non NEXT invasiv* or noninvasiv* or ablat*) near/2 cardiac near/1 (radiat* or irradiat*)):ti,ab,kw	0
13	((catheter* near/1 free) not (stuck* near/6 catheter*)):ti,ab,kw	55
14	((stereotact* and (radiother* or irradiat* or radiat* or ablat*)) or SBRT or SABR):ti,ab,kw	2125
15	((multi NEXT leaf or multileaf) near/2 collimator*) or (MLC NEXT track*)):ti,ab,kw	50
16	((heavy or carbon or C12 or (C NEXT 12) or 12C or (12 NEXT C)) near/3 ion*) or THIR):ti,ab,kw not ((heavy near/3 metal*) or (carbon NEXT dioxid*)):ti,ab,kw	173
17	((photon* or proton* or ion* or particle* or carbon* or C12 or (C NEXT 12) or 12C or (12 NEXT C)) near/2 (beam* or irradiat*)):ti,ab,kw	478
18	((proton* near/3 (therap* or radiother* or ablat*)) not (proton NEXT pump*)):ti,ab,kw	500
19	(Cyberknife or (Cyber NEXT knife) or Cyberheart or (Cyber NEXT heart)):ti,ab,kw	82
20	{or #11-#19} [radioablation]	3526
21	((cancer* or carcinom* or adenocarcinom* or tumor* or tumour* or neoplas* or malignan* or sarcom* or leiomyosarcom* or adenom* or metasta* or neoadjuv* or (neo NEXT adjuv*) or chemother* or cytostat* or (checkpoint NEXT inhib*) or prostat* or breast* or mastect* or postmastect* or thorax or thoracic or mediastin* or lobectom* or mesotheliom* or NSCLC* or cholangiocarcinom* or lymphom* or leukem* or leukaem* or AML or melanom* or schwannom* or NF2 or neurofibrom* or paragangliom* or gliom* or glioblastom*) not (fibrillat* or flutter or arrhythm* or tachycard* or cardiac or sinus or atrioventr* or atrium or ventricul*)):ti	219270
22	20 not 21 [radioablation (not cancer therapy as main topic)]	911
23	13 and 28 [I cardiac arrhythmias & radiotherapy]	25

Search engine: **Google Scholar**. Search strategy executed on: **2023-09-11**.

First 200 highest ranked hits

"radiosurgery"|"radioablation"|"radio-ablation"|"radio-surgery"|"heavy-ion irradiation"

"arrhythmias"|"arrhythmia"|"fibrillation"|"fibrillations"|"tachycardia"|"tachycardias"|"extrasystole"|"extrasystoles"

PRISMA 2020 flow diagram for new systematic reviews which included searches of databases and registers only

*Consider, if feasible to do so, reporting the number of records identified from each database or register searched (rather than the total number across all databases/registers).

**If automation tools were used, indicate how many records were excluded by a human and how many were excluded by automation tools.

From: Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71

For more information, visit: <http://www.prisma-statement.org/>

Supplementary File 6. Clinical characteristics

Clinical characteristics of the patients treated in prospective studies investigating the use of stereotactic arrhythmia radioablation for the treatment of ventricular tachycardia.

Publication year, Author	N	PVC as indication for STAR N (%)	Male sex N (%)	Median age (range)	Ischemic cardiomyopathy N (%)	Median LVEF (range)	Median prior CAs (range)	≥1 prior CA N (%)	≥1 prior epi-CA N (%)	NYHA I N (%)	NYHA II N (%)	NYHA III N (%)	NYHA IV N (%)	Class I AAD N (%)	Class II AAD N (%)	Class III AAD N (%)
Robinson et al. (2019) ¹	19	2 (11%)	17 (89%)	66 (49-81)	11 (58%)	25% (15-58%)	1 (0-4)	16 (84%)	n/a	1 (5%)	4 (21%)	10 (53%)	4 (21%)	11 (58%)	18 (95%)	19 (100%)
Gianni et al. (2020) ²	5	0 (0%)	5 (100%)	67 (45-76)	4 (80%)	25% (20-55%)	1 (1-2)	5 (100%)	1 (20%)	1 (20%)	4 (80%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	3 (60%)	n/a	5 (100%)
Carbucicchio et al. (2021) ³	#8	0 (0%)	8 (100%)	72 (59-81)	4 (50%)	21% (20-44%)	2 (0-5)	6 (75%)	2 (25%)	0 (0%)	2 (25%)	6 (75%)	0 (0%)	n/a	n/a	n/a
Molon et al. (2022) ⁴	6	0 (0%)	5 (83%)	80 (61-85)	4 (67%)	27% (20-42%)	0 (0-1)	2 (33%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (33%)	3 (50%)	1 (17%)	2 (33%)	6 (100%)	1 (17%)
Chang et al. (2022) ⁵	6	1 (17%)	4 (67%)	72 (63-85)	3 (50%)	32% (24-57%)	1 (0-2)	4 (67%)	n/a	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (33%)	4 (67%)	0 (0%)	5 (83%)	6 (100%)
^Krug et al. (2023) ⁶	5	0 (0%)	4 (80%)	67 (49-74)	2 (40%)	35% (20-45%)	3 (0-6)	4 (80%)	n/a	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	3 (60%)	1 (20%)	3 (60%)	4 (80%)	5 (50%)
Miszczyc et al. (2023) ⁷	11	0 (0%)	10 (91%)	67 (45-72)	9 (82%)	27% (20-40%)	1 (1-4)	11 (100%)	1 (9%)	1 (9%)	8 (73%)	2 (18%)	0 (0%)	4 (36%)	11 (100%)	4 (36%)
van der Ree et al. (2023) ⁸	6	0 (0%)	6 (100%)	73 (54-83)	6 (100%)	38% (24-52%)	2 (1-5)	6 (100%)	1 (17%)	0 (0%)	3 (50%)	3 (50%)	0 (0%)	5 (83%)	6 (100%)	5 (83%)
Amino et al. (2023) ⁹	3	0 (0%)	1 (33%)	71 (60-91)	2 (67%)	27% (20-65%)	0 (0-1)	1 (33%)	n/a	0 (0%)	1 (33%)	1 (33%)	1 (33%)	0 (0%)	3 (100%)	1 (33%)
Arkles et al. (2023) ¹⁰	#15	0 (0%)	13 (87%)	65* (n/a)	7 (54%)	30.2%* (n/a)	n/a	9 (60%)	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	14 (93%)

N – number of cases; PVC - premature ventricular contraction; n/a – not available; LVEF - left ventricular ejection fraction; (epi-)CA – (epicardial) catheter ablation; refers to the number of patients that had at least one (epi-)CA before cardiac stereotactic arrhythmia radioablation; NYHA - New York Heart Association Functional Classification; AAD - antiarrhythmic drugs

#In each of these studies one patient did not receive the prescribed treatment due to decline in health condition between enrolment and planned STAR

^NYHA assessed based on provided clinical data (missing for one patient); *mean

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1. Robinson CG, Samson PP, Moore KMS, Hugo GD, Knutson N, Mutic S, *et al.* Phase I/II Trial of Electrophysiology-Guided Noninvasive Cardiac Radioablation for Ventricular Tachycardia. *Circulation* 2019;**139**:313–21.
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9. Amino M, Kabuki S, Kunieda E, Hashimoto J, Sugawara A, Sakai T, *et al.* Interim Report of a Japanese Phase II Trial for Cardiac Stereotactic Body Radiotherapy in Refractory Ventricular Tachycardia — Focus on Target Determination —. *Circ Rep* 2023;**5**:69–79.
10. Arkles J, Markman T, Trevillian R, Yegya-Raman N, Garg L, Nazarian S, *et al.* One-year outcomes after stereotactic body radiotherapy for refractory ventricular tachycardia. *Heart Rhythm Elsevier*; 2024;**21**:18–24.

Supplementary File 7. Detailed characteristics of radiotherapy delivery in patients treated in prospective studies investigating the use of cardiac stereotactic body radiotherapy for the treatment of ventricular tachycardia.

a) Tabularised data

Date, Author	N	Targeting modalities	Target volume transfer quality assurance	Dose [Gy]	median (range) GTV/CTV [cc]	PTV margin [mm]	median (range) PTV [cc]	technique	Respiratory movement compensation	Dedicated OAR dose constraints
Robinson et al. (2019) ¹	19	cardiac CT, cardiac MRI, FDG-PET, ECGI , previous EAM , 12-lead ECG	17-segment model	25	25.4 (6.4 - 88.6)	5	98.9 (60.9 - 298.8)	C-arm	Abdominal compression and 4D-CT	No
Gianni et al. (2020) ²	5	cardiac CT, previous EAM , 12-lead ECG	CardioPlan software	25	n/a (n/a)	n/a	173 (80 - 184)	robotic	CyberKnife Synchrony using temporary right ventricle lead as a fiducial	No
Carbucicchio et al. (2021) ³	7	cardiac CT*, EAM or ECGI , 12-lead ECG	EAM/ECGI-CT image fusion	25	43.7 (14.1 - 55)	n/a	198.3 (88.1 - 239)	C-arm	4D-CT	No
Molon et al. (2022) ⁴	6	cardiac CT, FDG-PET, ECGI	Not specified	25	23.5 (10.4 - 74.5)	5	84.9 (47.3 - 196)	C-arm	4D-CT	No
Chang et al. (2022) ⁵	6	CT, MRI, or SPECT, previous EAM , 12-lead ECG	Not specified	25	10 (3 - 78.6)	5	52.2 (17.5 - 246.8)	C-arm	4D-CT	No
Krug et al. (2023) ⁶	5	contrast-enhanced ECG-gated CT, recent EAM , 12-lead ECG [^]	CARDIO-RT software	25	8.1 (6 - 34.4)	3-5	69.6 (43.4 - 80.7)	C-arm (80%); robotic (20%)	4D-CT (80%) Deep Inspiration Breath Hold (20%)	Yes
Miszczyc et al. (2023) ⁷	11	cardiac CT, EAM , 12-lead ECG [^]	Slicer-3D software by Hohmann et al.	25	27.7 (7.3 - 51.8)	3	73 (18.6 - 111.3)	C-arm	Deep Inspiration Breath Hold	Yes
van der Ree et al. (2023) ⁸	6	cardiac CT, ECGI , 12-lead ECG [^]	17-segment model	25	46 (15 - 87)	5	187 (93 - 372)	C-arm	4D-CT	No
Amino et al. (2023) ⁹	3	cardiac CT, MRI, nuclear imaging, EAM , echocardiography, 12-lead ECG	17-segment model	25	21.2 (8.3 - 24.2)	2-5	55 (49.7 - 96.4)	C-arm	Abdominal compression	No
Arkles et al. (2023) ¹⁰	14	CT, MRI, FDG-PET, EAM , channel prediction	Not specified	25	22.1 (11.3 - 46.7)	3	#84.7 (45.6 - 124.1)	C-arm	Abdominal compression and 4D-CT	Yes

CT – computed tomography; EAM – electroanatomic mapping (invasive); ECGI – electrocardiographic imaging (non-invasive); ECG – electrocardiography; FDG-PET - fluorodeoxyglucose-positron emission tomography; MRI – magnetic resonance imaging; SPECT – single-photon emission computed tomography; C-arm – any C-arm linear accelerator (e.g. VARIAN TrueBeam); robotic – in both cases refers to Accuray CyberKnife radiosurgery system; OAR - organs at risk.

*dual energy; ^authors indicate that any other available medical imaging was used to aid the target volume definition on a case-to-case basis; #The authors reported 45.6 (84.7-124.1) cc, which was assumed to be a typo, knowing that the mean and standard deviation were 84.9 ± 24.4 cc.

b) Additional descriptions of the available RT-related data

Robinson et al.

Procedural workflow, including target volume definition, transfer of the target volume to treatment-planning CT, and details of the radiotherapy planning and delivery are described in a Supplementary File attached to the manuscript, and in a previous article¹¹.

Target volume definition: Location of the first 10 ms of VT on the ECGI, and the full thickness of myocardial scar identified on medical imaging. The contoured volume was limited to regions of abnormal myocardium.

Target volume transfer QA: 17-segment heart model.

Respiratory motion compensation: Abdominal compression and 4D-CT ITV approach.

Dose constraints to OARs: not specified.

Gianni et al.

The treatment protocol is described in the manuscript; however, the workflow is not reproducible due to the use of proprietary software, and several characteristics are not well described (e.g. PTV margins, practical application of electrophysiologic data).

Target volume definition: Area of myocardial thinning on contrast-enhanced CT, correlated with low-voltage areas identified during previous EAM, and VT exit site identified through evaluation of 12-lead ECG morphology.

Target volume transfer QA: proprietary software (CardioPlan).

Respiratory motion compensation: CyberKnife Synchrony Respiratory Tracking System. An implanted transjugular temporary active fixation pacing lead placed in the right ventricular septal area was used as an fiducial for tracking.

Dose constraints to OARs: not specified.

Carbucchio et al.

Procedural workflow, including target volume definition and basic details of the radiotherapy planning and delivery are described in a separate article¹².

Target volume definition: Area of myocardial thinning and delayed contrast enhancement on CT, correlated with low-voltage areas identified during EAM (< 0.5 mV).

Target volume transfer QA: image fusion (details not specified).

Respiratory motion compensation: 4D-CT ITV approach.

Dose constraints to OARs: not specified.

Molon et al.

Basic characteristics of the target volume definition and radiotherapy planning are described in the article.

Target volume definition: Location of the first 10 ms of VT on the ECGI combined with FDG-PET data and other available radiological imaging; details not specified.

Target volume transfer QA: not specified.

Respiratory motion compensation: 4D-CT ITV approach.

Dose constraints to OARs: not specified.

Chang et al.

Basic characteristics of the target volume definition and radiotherapy planning are described in the article.

Target volume definition: A synthesis of imaging and electrophysiological data; details not specified.

Target volume transfer QA: not specified.

Respiratory motion compensation: 4D-CT ITV approach.

Dose constraints to OARs: not specified.

Krug et al.

Procedural workflow, including target volume definition, transfer of the target volume to treatment-planning CT, and details of the radiotherapy planning and delivery are described in the manuscript, and in a previous article¹³.

Target volume definition: A synthesis of medical imaging and electroanatomic data; methodology validated in a benchmark study.

Target volume transfer QA: CARDIO-RT software (available free-of-charge upon request)¹⁴.

Respiratory motion compensation: 4D-CT ITV approach (80%) or Deep Inspiration Breath Hold (20%).

Dose constraints to OARs: specified in a previous article¹³.

Miszczyk et al.

Procedural workflow, including target volume definition, transfer of the target volume to treatment-planning CT, and details of the radiotherapy planning and delivery are described in the manuscript, and in a previous article¹⁵.

Target volume definition: A synthesis of medical imaging and electroanatomic data; fibrotic tissue defined as bipolar voltage < 0.5 MV on EAM.

Target volume transfer QA: Mainly Slicer3D-based software by Hohmann et al. (available free of charge)¹⁶. Additionally, 17-segment heart model and CARDIO-RT.

Respiratory motion compensation: Deep Inspiration Breath Hold.

Dose constraints to OARs: specified in a previous article¹⁵.

van der Ree et al.

Basic characteristics of the target volume definition and radiotherapy planning are described in the article.

Target volume definition: A synthesis of imaging and electrophysiological data; details not specified.

Target volume transfer QA: 17-segment heart model.

Respiratory motion compensation: 4D-CT ITV approach.

Dose constraints to OARs: not specified.

Amino et al.

Treatment workflow described in the article; refers to the previously described method by the Washington University team¹⁷.

Target volume definition: a synthesis of imaging, electrophysiological, and functional data plotted on the 17-segment heart model.

Target volume transfer QA: 17-segment heart model.

Respiratory motion compensation: abdominal compression.

Dose constraints to OARs: not specified.

Arkles et al.

Basic characteristics of the target volume definition and radiotherapy planning are described in the article.

Target volume definition: a synthesis of imaging and electrophysiological data.

Target volume transfer QA: not specified.

Respiratory motion compensation: abdominal compression and 4D-CT ITV approach.

Dose constraints to OARs: listed in a supplementary file.

References:

1. Robinson CG, Samson PP, Moore KMS, Hugo GD, Knutson N, Mutic S, *et al.* Phase I/II Trial of Electrophysiology-Guided Noninvasive Cardiac Radioablation for Ventricular Tachycardia. *Circulation* 2019;**139**:313–21.
2. Gianni C, Rivera D, Burkhardt JD, Pollard B, Gardner E, Maguire P, *et al.* Stereotactic arrhythmia radioablation for refractory scar-related ventricular tachycardia. *Heart Rhythm* Elsevier; 2020;**17**:1241–8.
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Supplementary File 8. Risk of Bias assessment using ROBINS-I tool

Overall Risk of Bias assessment:

Author	Study title	Overall RoB
Robinson et al. (2019)	Phase I/II Trial of Electrophysiology-Guided Noninvasive Cardiac Radioablation for Ventricular Tachycardia	Low
Gianni et al. (2020)	Stereotactic arrhythmia radioablation for refractory scar-related ventricular tachycardia	Moderate
Carbucicchio et al. (2021)	Stereotactic radioablation for the treatment of ventricular tachycardia: preliminary data and insights from the STRA-MI-VT phase Ib/II study	Moderate
Chang et al. (2022)	Short-term and long-term effects of noninvasive cardiac radioablation for ventricular tachycardia: A single-center case series	Serious
Molon et al. (2022)	Stereotactic ablative radiotherapy in patients with refractory ventricular tachyarrhythmia	Serious
Arkles et al. (2023)	One-year outcomes after stereotactic body radiotherapy for refractory ventricular tachycardia	Moderate
Amino et al. (2023)	Interim Report of a Japanese Phase II Trial for Cardiac Stereotactic Body Radiotherapy in Refractory Ventricular Tachycardia	Moderate
Krug et al. (2023)	Radiosurgery for ventricular tachycardia (RAVENTA): interim analysis of a multicenter multiplatform feasibility trial	Moderate
Miszczyk et al. (2023)	Stereotactic management of arrhythmia - radiosurgery in treatment of ventricular tachycardia (SMART-VT). Results of a prospective safety trial	Moderate
Van der Ree et al. (2023)	Non-invasive stereotactic arrhythmia radiotherapy for ventricular tachycardia: results of the prospective STARNL-1 trial	Moderate

Risk of Bias assessment for specific domains:

Author	Confounding	Selection participants	Class. interv.	Dev. intend. interv.	Missing data	Measurement bias	Selection rep. results
Robinson et al. (2019)	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Gianni et al. (2020)	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Low
Carbucicchio et al. (2021)	Low	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Low
Chang et al. (2022)	Low	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Serious
Molon et al. (2022)	No information	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Serious	Serious
Arkles et al. (2023)	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Low
Amino et al. (2023)	No information	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Low
Krug et al. (2023)	No information	Moderate	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Low
Miszczyk et al. (2023)	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Low
Van der Ree et al. (2023)	Low	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	Low

Additional comments for conflicts resolved through mediation with a third author:

Author	Domain of bias	Discussion
Robinson et al. (2019)	Measurement bias	Although efficacy and safety endpoints were not independently assessed, the authors report a standard operating procedure (SOP) for ICD programming, and the authors actively describe how adverse events (AEs) are scored. The authors also included a detailed Supplementary File describing all AEs, not exclusive to the assumed 90 days period, and the AEs were scored conservatively with regard to their attribution (even though the assessment was performed by the study team). Therefore, we deemed the risk of measurement bias to be low.
Gianni et al. (2020)	Missing data	Although missing data associated with patients' death could affect the 12-month outcomes reported by the authors, it is believed that the article sufficiently indicated the timing of patients' deaths for the reader to properly interpret the data.
	Measurement bias	That the authors did not sufficiently standardize the reporting of adverse events, including lack of attribution assessment. It is possible that the knowledge of the intervention affected the reporting. In particular, some high-grade adverse events are known to occur spontaneously in this group of patients, yet have not been reported.
Carbucicchio et al. (2021)	Missing data	Many baseline characteristics possibly associated with outcomes were missing, including scarce details of the previous ventricular tachycardia (VT) treatments. Moreover, there was missing follow-up data on some of the patients, and one did not receive intervention at all. We believe that the study should be rated at at least moderate risk of bias in this domain.
Chang et al. (2022)	Confounding	Due to the lack of a detailed description of ICD programming, this was initially scored as a potential confounding factor. However, after discussion, it was classified as a potential measurement bias instead, and therefore scored accordingly.
	Selection bias	The authors did not describe well how they selected the candidates for treatment, and if there were any treated cases which they excluded from the study, making the study prone to selection bias.
	Selective reporting	Partial remission versus complete remission was discussed, but no reduction percentage thresholds were described in the methods, nor individual data on reduction in VT burden was provided. The reporting appears therefore to be selective, because the data was reported as a model which was not previously specified.
Molon et al. (2022)	Confounding	No information about previous patients' treatments provided.
	Missing data	Many baseline characteristics possibly associated with outcomes were missing, including scarce details of the previous ventricular tachycardia (VT) treatments. Moreover, there was missing follow-up data on some of the patients. Despite the fact that we obtained additional information through contacting the authors, we believe

that the study should be rated at at least moderate risk of bias in this domain.

Arkles et al. (2023)	Confounding	Due to the lack of a detailed description of ICD programming, this was initially scored as a potential confounding factor. However, after discussion, it was classified as a potential measurement bias instead, and scored accordingly.
	Missing data	Initially conservatively scored as moderate due to the interference between mortality and efficacy assessment; however, after detailed analysis, we decided that the authors report data in detail, and performed the analyses according to the protocol, well enough not to raise concerns about the validity of data reporting.
Amino et al. (2023)	Confounding	No information about additional patients' treatments provided.
	Selection bias	The authors did not describe well how they selected the candidates for treatment, and if there were any treated cases which they excluded from the study, making the study prone to selection bias.
	Measurement bias	The authors do not clearly describe how the ICD treatment settings were adjusted, only the ICD pacing programming, which can influence the results as the VT burden was measured based on the ICD records.
Krug et al. (2023)	Confounding	No information about additional patients' treatments provided.
	Missing data	Many clinical characteristics of the patients were missing, including NYHA scale. The data was partially retrieved after contacting the authors, nevertheless, we believe that the study should be scored as 'moderate risk of bias' in this domain'.
	Selection bias	The authors do not describe how they selected their participants during screening (e.g., whether all consecutive cases fulfilling the inclusion criteria were enrolled, or the investigators selectively chosen participants)
Miszczyk et al. (2023)	Confounding	Due to the lack of a detailed description of ICD programming, this was initially scored as a potential confounding factor. However, after discussion, it was classified as a potential measurement bias, and therefore scored accordingly.
van der Ree et al. (2023)	Missing data	In the case of a patient not completing 12-month follow-up, the authors do describe they compared the same period before and after treatment. However, it could be imaginable that patients suffered from less VT episodes 12 months before inclusion to the trial, which are the months that are to be excluded. Conversely, patients that died could be the worst patients, who could have suffered from VT episodes after their death. Therefore, the risk of bias due to missing data was deemed moderate.

van der Ree
et al. (2023)

Measurement
bias

Although efficacy and safety endpoints were not independently assessed, the authors report a SOP for ICD programming and the authors actively describe how AEs are scored, and that they did so conservatively (even though it is performed by the study team itself). Therefore, we deemed the risk of measurement bias to be low.

Supplementary File 9. Treatment-related adverse events

List of possibly, probably or definitely treatment-related grade 3 or worse adverse events within 90 days after treatment in prospective studies evaluating the use of stereotactic arrhythmia radioablation for the treatment of therapy-refractory ventricular tachycardia. The definitions of adverse events according to the Common Terminology Criteria for Adverse Events v5.0 are described in another table below.

Publication year, Author	N	N events	Event description: grade (CTCAE); attribution; CTCAE term and timing (days after STAR); additional explanation (if applicable)
Robinson et al. (2019) ¹	19	2	1) G3; possibly related; heart failure at 65 days; exacerbation of pre-existing heart failure. 2) G3; probably related; pericarditis at 80 days; symptoms improved following treatment with prednisone.
Gianni et al. (2020) ²	5	0	
Carbucicchio et al. (2021) ³	7	0	
Molon et al. (2022) ⁴	6	1	1) G5; possibly related; heart failure at 30 days; heart failure exacerbation leading to death due to end-stage heart failure.
Chang et al. (2022) ⁵	6	1	1) *G3; ^attribution not specified; heart failure between 1 st month and 1-year follow-up; heart failure exacerbation requiring insertion of a left ventricular assist device.
Krug et al. (2023) ⁶	5	0	
Miszczyk et al. (2023) ⁷	11	1	1) G4; possibly related, heart failure at 87 days; heart failure exacerbation which subsided following conservative treatment with intravenous inotropic agents, diuretics, and levosimendan.
van der Ree et al. (2023) ⁸	6	0	
Amino et al. (2023) ⁹	3	1	1) G3; ^attribution not specified; heart failure at 53 days; exacerbation which led to short hospitalisation, and improved after treatment with diuretics.
Arkles et al. (2023) ¹⁰	14	3	1) G5; #possibly related; aspiration pneumonia at 10 day; death due to pneumonia. 2) G5, possibly related, heart failure at 12 days; death due to cardiogenic shock. 3) G5, #possibly related, right ventricular dysfunction at 3 months; progressive right ventricular failure with cirrhosis.

CTCAE – Common Toxicity Criteria for Adverse Events; STAR – STereotactic Arrhythmia Radioablation; *not possible to determine whether the AE occurred in the first 90 days; ^all ≥G3 adverse events with unspecified attribution were considered as at least “possibly related”; however, it is important to note that ≥G3 adverse events scored as unrelated were not included; #the description of the attribution could also be interpreted as “unlikely”

Definitions of previously referenced adverse events according to: Common Terminology Criteria for Adverse Events (CTCAE), version 5.0, published November 27, 2017. U.S. Department of Health and Human Services. National Institutes of Health. National Cancer Institute. https://ctep.cancer.gov/protocolDevelopment/electronic_applications/ctc.htm (accessed: 2024/07/10).

CTCAE Term	Grade 1	Grade 2	Grade 3	Grade 4	Grade 5
Heart failure	Asymptomatic with laboratory (e.g., BNP [B-Natriuretic Peptide]) or cardiac imaging abnormalities	Symptoms with moderate activity or exertion	Symptoms at rest or with minimal activity or exertion; hospitalization; new onset of symptoms	Life-threatening consequences; urgent intervention indicated (e.g., continuous IV therapy or mechanical hemodynamic support)	Death
Pericarditis	Asymptomatic, ECG or physical findings (e.g., rub) consistent with pericarditis	Symptomatic pericarditis (e.g., chest pain)	Pericarditis with physiologic consequences (e.g., pericardial constriction)	Life-threatening consequences; urgent intervention indicated	Death
Lung infection	-	Moderate symptoms; oral intervention indicated (e.g., antibiotic, antifungal, or antiviral)	IV antibiotic, antifungal, or antiviral intervention indicated; invasive intervention indicated	Life-threatening consequences; urgent intervention indicated	Death
Aspiration	Asymptomatic; clinical or diagnostic observations only; intervention not indicated	Altered eating habits; coughing or choking episodes after eating or swallowing; medical intervention indicated (e.g., suction or oxygen)	Dyspnea and pneumonia symptoms (e.g., aspiration pneumonia); hospitalization indicated; unable to aliment orally	Life-threatening respiratory or hemodynamic compromise; intubation or urgent intervention indicated	Death
Comment: in cases of lung infection (e.g. pneumonia) due to aspiration, CTCAE guide suggests using the "Aspiration" term for reporting.					
Right ventricular dysfunction	Asymptomatic with laboratory (e.g., BNP [B-Natriuretic Peptide]) or cardiac imaging abnormalities	Symptoms with moderate activity or exertion	Severe symptoms, associated with hypoxia, right heart failure; oxygen indicated	Life-threatening consequences; urgent intervention indicated (e.g., ventricular assist device); heart transplant indicated	Death

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A) Funnel plot for Figure 1 (rate of grade 3 or worse adverse events)

B) Funnel plot for Figure 2 (1-year overall survival)

C) Funnel plot for Figure 3 (1-year recurrence-free survival)

D) Funnel plot for Supplementary Figure 11B (95% reduction)

E) Funnel plot for Supplementary Figure 11C (75% reduction)

F) Funnel plot for Supplementary Figure 11D (50% reduction)

G) Funnel plot for Supplementary Figure 12 (1-year time-to-recurrence)

H) Funnel plot for Supplementary Figure 13A (sensitivity analysis for rate of adverse events)

I) Funnel plot for Supplementary Figure 13B (sensitivity analysis for overall survival)

Supplementary File 11. Arrhythmia burden reduction

A) Visualisation of the time frames used for VT burden reduction calculation

A) Time frames as originally reported by the authors

B) Adjusted time frames

B) Proportion of patients experiencing $\geq 95\%$ VT burden reduction after STAR

Study **Cases Total Proportion** **95% C.I.**

Time frame: -6 to 0 vs. 1.5 to 6 months (6-week blanking period)

Robinson et al. (2019)	11	18	0.61 [0.36; 0.83]
Molon et al. (2022)	3	5	0.60 [0.15; 0.95]
Amino et al. (2023)	2	3	0.67 [0.09; 0.99]
Arkles et al. (2023)	9	12	0.75 [0.43; 0.95]
van der Ree et al. (2023)	2	6	0.33 [0.04; 0.78]
Random effects model	44		0.61 [0.40; 0.79]

Heterogeneity: $Q = 2.73$ ($p = 0.6$)

Time frame: -3 to 0 vs. 3 to 6 months (3-month blanking period)

Gianni et al. (2020)	1	4	0.25 [0.01; 0.81]
Carbucicchio et al. (2021)	2	4	0.50 [0.07; 0.93]
Miszczyk et al. (2023)	7	9	0.78 [0.40; 0.97]
Random effects model	17		0.58 [0.09; 0.95]

Heterogeneity: $Q = 2.96$ ($p = 0.2$)

Random effects model

61 **0.61 [0.45; 0.74]**

Heterogeneity: $Q = 5.73$ ($p = 0.6$)

C) Proportion of patients experiencing $\geq 75\%$ VT burden reduction after STAR

Study **Cases Total Proportion** **95% C.I.**

Time frame: -6 to 0 vs. 1.5 to 6 months (6-week blanking period)

Robinson et al. (2019)	16	18	0.89	[0.65; 0.99]
Molon et al. (2022)	3	5	0.60	[0.15; 0.95]
Amino et al. (2023)	2	3	0.67	[0.09; 0.99]
Arkles et al. (2023)	10	12	0.83	[0.52; 0.98]
van der Ree et al. (2023)	6	6	1.00	[0.54; 1.00]
Random effects model	44		0.84	[0.63; 0.94]

Heterogeneity: $Q = 2.41$ ($p = 0.7$)

Time frame: -3 to 0 vs. 3 to 6 months (3-month blanking period)

Gianni et al. (2020)	1	4	0.25	[0.01; 0.81]
Carbucicchio et al. (2021)	4	4	1.00	[0.40; 1.00]
Miszczyk et al. (2023)	7	9	0.78	[0.40; 0.97]
Random effects model	17		0.73	[0.04; 0.99]

Heterogeneity: $Q = 2.8$ ($p = 0.3$)

Random effects model

61 **0.80 [0.62; 0.91]**

Heterogeneity: $Q = 6.49$ ($p = 0.5$)

D) Proportion of patients experiencing $\geq 50\%$ VT burden reduction after STAR

Study **Cases Total Proportion** **95% C.I.**

Time frame: -6 to 0 vs. 1.5 to 6 months (6-week blanking period)

Robinson et al. (2019)	17	18	0.94	[0.73; 1.00]
Molon et al. (2022)	5	5	1.00	[0.48; 1.00]
Amino et al. (2023)	2	3	0.67	[0.09; 0.99]
Arkles et al. (2023)	10	12	0.83	[0.52; 0.98]
van der Ree et al. (2023)	6	6	1.00	[0.54; 1.00]
Random effects model	44		0.91	[0.70; 0.98]

Heterogeneity: $Q = 1.88$ ($p = 0.8$)

Time frame: -3 to 0 vs. 3 to 6 months (3-month blanking period)

Gianni et al. (2020)	3	4	0.75	[0.19; 0.99]
Carbucicchio et al. (2021)	4	4	1.00	[0.40; 1.00]
Miszczyk et al. (2023)	8	9	0.89	[0.52; 1.00]
Random effects model	17		0.88	[0.23; 0.99]

Heterogeneity: $Q = 0.39$ ($p = 0.8$)

Random effects model

61 **0.90 [0.77; 0.96]**

Heterogeneity: $Q = 2.3$ ($p > 0.9$)

A) Sensitivity analysis for G3 or worse adverse events (excluding studies with high Risk of Bias)

B) Sensitivity analysis for 1-year overall survival (excluding studies with high Risk of Bias)

Study	Cases	Total	Proportion	95% C.I.
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Robinson et al. (2019)	14	19	0.74	[0.49; 0.91]
Gianni et al. (2020)	3	5	0.60	[0.15; 0.95]
Carbucicchio et al. (2021)	3	7	0.43	[0.10; 0.82]
Krug et al. (2023)	4	5	0.80	[0.28; 0.99]
Miszczyk et al. (2023)	9	11	0.82	[0.48; 0.98]
van der Ree et al. (2023)	4	6	0.67	[0.22; 0.96]
Amino et al. (2023)	3	3	1.00	[0.29; 1.00]
Arkles et al. (2023)	10	14	0.71	[0.42; 0.92]

Random effects model
 Heterogeneity $Q = 3.54$ ($p = 0.8$)

70 **0.71 [0.57; 0.82]**

Supplementary File 14. Input data for the time-to-event analyses

List of study group sizes, probabilities, and corresponding standard errors calculated using the Kaplan-Meier method in individual studies, which were used to calculate the meta-analytic averages for 1-year overall survival, freedom from recurrence, and recurrence-free survival.

Publication year, 1st author	N (OS)	1-y OS	1-y OS SE	N (FFR)	1-y FFR	1-y FFR SE	N (RFS)	1-y RFS	1-y RFS SE
Robinson et al. (2019) ¹	19	0.737	0.101	17	0.156	0.0973	17	0.1176	0.0781
Gianni et al. (2020) ²	5	0.6	0.219	5	0	0	5	0	0
Carbucicchio et al. (2021) ³	7	0.457	0.224	4	0	0	7	0	0
Molon et al. (2022) ⁴	6	0.833	0.152	5	0.6	0.219	6	0.5	0.204
Chang et al. (2022) ⁵	6	0.833	0.152	6	0.5	0.204	n/a	n/a	n/a
Krug et al. (2023) ⁶	5	0.8	0.179	5	0.6	0.219	5	0.6	0.219
Miszczuk et al. (2023) ⁷	11	0.808	0.122	10	0.267	0.15	11	0.182	0.116
van der Ree et al. (2023) ⁸	6	0.667	0.192	6	0.167	0.152	6	0.167	0.152
Amino et al. (2023) ⁹	3	1	0	3	0.667	0.272	3	0.667	0.272
Arkles et al. (2023) ¹⁰	14	0.714	0.121	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a

SE – standard error; OS – overall survival; FFR – freedom from recurrence; RFS – recurrence-free survival; n/a – not available

Supplementary File legend:

Supplementary File 1. PRISMA 2020 checklist

Supplementary File 2. PRISMA 2020 for abstract checklist

Supplementary File 3. PICOS framework

Supplementary File 4. Search strategy

Supplementary File 5. PRISMA flow diagram

Supplementary File 6. Clinical characteristics of the patients treated in prospective studies investigating the use of STAR for the treatment of VT

Supplementary File 7. Detailed characteristics of radiotherapy delivery in patients treated in prospective studies investigating the use of STAR for the treatment of VT.

Supplementary File 8. Risk of Bias assessment using ROBINS-I tool

Supplementary File 9. Descriptions of treatment-related adverse events in the first 90 days after STAR

Supplementary File 10. Funnel plots

Supplementary File 11. Analysis of arrhythmia burden reduction

Supplementary File 12. One-year freedom from recurrence after STAR

Supplementary File 13. Sensitivity analyses

Supplementary File 14. Input data for the time-to-event analyses